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1 *bcgTree*: automatized phylogenetic tree building from bacterial core 2 genomes

3 Markus J. Ankenbrand¹ and Alexander Keller^{1§}

4¹ Department of Animal Ecology and Tropical Biology, University of Würzburg,
5 Germany

6[§] Corresponding author

7

8 Abstract

9 The need for multi-gene analyses in scientific fields such as phylogenetics and
10 DNA barcoding has increased in recent years. In particular, these approaches are
11 increasingly important for differentiating bacterial species, where reliance on the
12 standard 16S rDNA marker can result in poor resolution.

13 Additionally, the assembly of bacterial genomes has become a standard task due
14 to advances in next-generation sequencing technologies. We created a
15 bioinformatic pipeline, *bcgTree*, which uses assembled bacterial genomes either
16 from databases or own sequencing results from the user to reconstruct their
17 phylogenetic history. The pipeline automatically extracts 107 essential single-
18 copy core genes, found in a majority of bacteria, using hidden Markov models and
19 performs a partitioned maximum-likelihood analysis.

20 Here, we describe the workflow of *bcgTree* and, as a proof-of-concept, its
21 usefulness in resolving the phylogeny of 293 publically available bacterial strains
22 of the genus *Lactobacillus*. We also evaluate its performance in both low- and
23 high-level taxonomy test sets. The tool is freely available at *github*
24 (<https://github.com/iimog/bcgTree>) and our institutional homepage
25 (<http://www.dna-analytics.biozentrum.uni-wuerzburg.de>).

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29

30Introduction

31Resolving the evolutionary and taxonomic relationships of organisms by DNA
32sequence data has a long history in bacteria (Cavalier-Smith, 1993; Woese and
33Fox, 1977; Woese, 1987). Morphologically, bacteria are hard to distinguish and
34classify, making DNA barcoding and molecular phylogenetics the methods of
35choice for researchers attempting to determine the relationships of bacterial
36strains. However, resolving phylogenetic relationships through the use of DNA
37sequences can be a challenging task. Selecting an appropriate genetic marker, one
38with both sufficient information for distinguishing taxa and with sufficient
39homology to make comparisons valid and conclusive (Capella-Gutierrez et al.,
402014; Wu et al., 2013), is essential for a correct reconstruction. Often, different
41markers are used for low-level (strain/species/genus) and high-level
42(family/class/order/phylum) phylogenetic analyses to compensate for this trade-
43off between information and conservation (Capella-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Wu et
44al., 2013).

45In bacteria, the 16S rDNA is currently the unrivaled and universally applied
46marker of choice for most phylogenetic and ecological studies. In this marker,
47several variable and conserved regions are present, allowing good amplification
48of sufficiently informative regions and differentiation of closely related taxa. The
4916S rDNA is well conserved across all prokaryotic species, allowing comparisons
50between phyla. But still this approach has its limitations, both regarding high-
51and low-level analyses (Capella-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2013). The
52bacterial phylogeny is still unresolved at its basal branches and it is unlikely that
53these will be resolved using a single marker. Furthermore, 16S sequences can be
54identical between strains despite massive genomic reorganisation, precluding the
55ability of this marker to differentiate certain genetically different strains with
56varied ecological functions (Jaspers and Overmann, 2004). In addition, ribosomal
57rDNA is present in multiple copies in each genome and intra-genomic variability
58is possible (Větrovský and Baldrian, 2013). Both effects may confuse the
59interpretation of taxonomic assignments, especially in functional or ecological
60analyses, as well as mutualistic or pathogenic host-bacteria associations.

61 While 16S rDNA-based phylogenetic analysis has been of great importance in
62 understanding the identity and evolutionary associations of bacteria, there are
63 several drawbacks to calculating a tree on a single marker sequence. Current
64 advances in high throughput sequencing technologies allow broader analysis
65 beyond this single marker convention. Bacterial genomes are usually of limited
66 size relative to the majority of eukaryotes, ranging from 130 kbp to 14 Mbp. The
67 drops in price per basepair and the small genome sizes make it feasible to
68 sequence a complete bacterial genome even for working groups with limited
69 funding (Keller et al., 2014; Metzker, 2009). This also leads to increasing
70 numbers of complete bacterial genomes being sequenced and deposited in public
71 databases (Pruitt et al., 2007; Uchiyama et al., 2013).

72 However deriving a phylogeny from whole genomes bears its own challenges. For
73 example, there are usually large genomic regions with no apparent similarities.
74 Also, those regions with homologies need to be extracted for downstream
75 phylogenetic analysis, a process requiring extensive bioinformatic expertise. One
76 way to address this challenge is to build a database of pre-calculated alignments
77 of tight genomic clusters (ATGC, Novichkov et al., 2009), enabling high resolution
78 micro-evolutionary analyses. Yet, this approach is limited as only a fraction of the
79 available genomes are included and it is not possible to supplement the analysis
80 with user-provided data. One solution to this problem is to concentrate on the
81 conserved regions present in a majority of organisms of interest (Ciccarelli et al.,
82 2006).

83 Here we present *bcgTree*, a tool that identifies and extracts a set of 107 essential
84 single-copy genes from amino-acid sequences of whole-genome data. The
85 definition of “essential core genes” used here is based on the work of Dupont et
86 al. (2012) and follows a statistical, not biological, argument. Our software
87 automatically compiles the core gene sequence data and uses it to reconstruct a
88 phylogenetic tree using a partitioned maximum likelihood analysis. For
89 validation purposes, we applied *bcgTree* to resolve the phylogeny of the genus
90 *Lactobacillus* including most genomes currently available for the Lactobacillales.
91 Additionally, test sets of high-level and low-level phylogenetic analysis were
92 directly compared to corresponding 16S rDNA trees for evaluation purposes.

93Materials and methods

94The *bcgTree* pipeline

95The principal workflow of *bcgTree* is as follows (Fig. 1): As input files, protein
96fasta (often defined as .faa) sequences can be used directly, for example those
97deposited in the Genome database of *NCBI* (Pruitt et al., 2007) or obtained by
98protein reading frame prediction tools. Each of those proteome sets are then
99searched for 107 essential bacterial single-copy genes (Dupont et al., 2012) using
100*hmmsearch* (version 3.1b1 (Eddy, 2010)). After completing this search for each
101organism, the tool generates an overall presence/absence table, which can be
102used for validation purposes, such as whether the majority of genes have been
103found (compare to Supplementary File 1).

104For each gene, the sequences of the best hit above a gene-specific cut-off are
105obtained from each proteome and stored in a gene-specific fasta file using the
106*SeqFilter* obtained from *proovread* (Hackl et al., 2014). Those gene-wise sequence
107sets are then aligned using *muscle* (v3.8.31, (Edgar, 2004)). Alignments are
108refined using *Gblocks* (version 0.91b, (Castresana, 2000; Talavera and Castresana,
1092007)) to avoid over-extensive gapped areas and highly misaligned regions
110obtained via the automation procedure. In case a gene was not found within a
111specific proteome, alignments of these genes are supplemented with completely
112gapped sequences for this organism.

113All gene-alignments are then concatenated and a partitioning file is generated to
114mark the boundaries of each gene. A tree is calculated on this concatenated
115alignment using *RAxML* (version 8.2.4, (Stamatakis, 2014)). Models are estimated
116individually for each original gene region by using the partition file. The final
117output is a maximum-likelihood tree with bootstrap support values. Several
118parameters for the internal programs (e.g. number of bootstraps, number of
119threads) can be adjusted by the user.

120The tool is executed as a *Perl* script from the command line or with a graphical
121user interface written in *Java*. It is available as source code and executable via
122<https://github.com/iimog/bcgTree>. This page also includes detailed installation
123instructions and lists the dependencies on other software tools.

124

125 *Selection of hidden Markov models (HMMs) used for searches*

126 The HMMs of the 107 essential single copy genes were taken from *TIGRFAM* (Haft
127 et al., 2003) and *Pfam* (Finn et al., 2010) as described by Dupont et al. (2012). In
128 Dupont et al. (2012), these HMMs were found to be present in more than 95% of
129 all bacteria. Further, all but four of the genes (*glyS*, *proS*, *rpoC* and *pheT*) were
130 represented by only one HMM, with the remaining four being represented by two
131 HMMs. As such, the latter HMMs are treated separately in the workflow due to
132 the high sequence dissimilarity. Approximately half of these genes encode
133 ribosomal proteins, and given that we found all of them on the chromosome of
134 *Lactobacillus acidophilus* strain 30SC, they are unlikely to be found on plasmids.

135

136 *Case study: Lactobacillus phylogeny*

137 As a case study, the phylogeny of the Lactobacillales has been reconstructed
138 using *bcgTree*. Genomes for this study have been taken from the EzGenome
139 database (<http://www.ezbiocloud.net/ezgenome>, accessed January 2016). The
140 2225 genomes found by searching for Lactobacillales included 293 genomes of
141 the genus *Lactobacillus*. The most dominant groups were *Streptococcus* (1188
142 genomes) and *Enterococcus* (622 genomes). As the focus of this case study was
143 the analysis of the *Lactobacillus* phylogeny, only 50 random genomes of
144 *Streptococcus* and *Enterococcus* each were used, but all of the remaining groups.
145 The resulting dataset contained the protein sequences from 515 Lactobacillales
146 genomes. Then, *bcgTree* was used with default parameters. All computation was
147 performed on an Ubuntu 12.04 LTS 64bit machine with an 80 core Intel(R)
148 Xeon(R) CPU E7- 4850 processing system and 512 GB of RAM). The resulting
149 tree is discussed here to address several questions regarding the *Lactobacillus*
150 phylogeny and the current All-Species Living Tree (Yarza et al., 2008).

151

152 *Comparison with 16S phylogeny and multi-marker benefit*

153 Two evaluation sets of smaller sample size were used for the evaluation of our
154 tool beyond the case study. This was done in direct comparison with a

155corresponding 16S tree that was reconstructed, as described below, using
156sequence data from the same bacterial strains.

157*Evaluation set 1*: To demonstrate the utility of *bcgTree* on low-level taxonomy, the
158software was applied to a subset of the case study sequences, i.e. only the genus
159*Lactobacillus*, and only those genomes represented at the *NCBI* genome database
160(accession date: October 2015, (Pruitt et al., 2007)), which resulted in 68
161*Lactobacillus* genomes. In this database the 16S data is readily accessible
162alongside the proteomes (Pruitt et al., 2007). As an outgroup, eleven genomes
163from the genus *Paenibacillus* were added. The amino acid sequences were
164downloaded from *NCBI*
165(<ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/Bacteria/all.faa.tar.gz>). The different files
166for plasmids and chromosomes were combined into a single fasta file for each
167genome. Then *bcgTree* analysis was performed on those 68 genomes with default
168parameters.

169*Evaluation set 2*: The high-level taxonomy evaluation set contains two arbitrarily
170chosen genomes each from most of the distinguished bacterial high-level groups.
171These include the two gram-positive clades Firmicutes and Actinobacteria, the
172PVC group and the FCB group, five subgroups of Proteobacteria (alpha, beta,
173gamma, delta and epsilon) and the Thermotogae. Two archaeal genomes were
174used as an outgroup.

175For both evaluation sets, the corresponding 16S rDNA gene tree was calculated
176for exactly the same genomes using the same steps of alignment with *muscle*,
177refinement with *Gblocks* and tree building with *RAxML* to maximize
178comparability between the approaches. 16S rRNA genes were extracted from
179*NCBI* (<ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/Bacteria/all.frn.tar.gz>, accession date:
180October 2015). In cases where multiple reference 16S rRNA sequences were
181available, only the longest was used. For one organism (*Lactobacillus brevis*
182KB290) the .frn file was missing. Thus, we used *RNAmmer* (version 1.2, (Lagesen
183et al., 2007)) to extract the the 16S sequence of this organism from the whole
184genome sequence.

185The robustness of the trees generated by *bcgTree* and 16S respectively was
186evaluated by bootstrap values obtained with both approaches. Bootstrap support

187 values for all nodes together were statistically compared by using a Student's t
188 test in *R* (R Development Core Team, 2010). Tree topologies for both evaluation
189 sets were compared between *bcgTree* and 16S using the *R* package *dendextend*
190 (Galili, 2015) for tanglegrams. Differences in topologies were highlighted using
191 the same package with dashed lines.

192 The influence of the number of genes used for the tree-building process on the
193 accuracy of the resulting tree was also assessed. For this, we used the final
194 alignment files obtained through *bcgTree* for both evaluation sets with all 109
195 partitions (two of the 107 genes have two partitions each). These were randomly
196 subsampled using *RAxML* and their corresponding partitions in the alignment
197 excluded. For both evaluation sets, we used this approach to create concatenated
198 alignment files with 1 to 107 random genes with ten replicates per number.
199 *RAxML*-derived trees were constructed using these alignments without
200 bootstrapping and with the same parameters used in the default *bcgTree* analysis.
201 The Quartet-Distances between the resulting trees and the full gene set tree was
202 calculated using *qdist* (version 2.0) (Mailund and Pedersen, 2004). The Quartet-
203 Distance is a measure of the topological distance between two phylogenetic trees
204 (Keller et al., 2010; Mailund and Pedersen, 2004). For visualization purposes, the
205 number of genes was rounded to increments of five. The Quartet-Distance of the
206 16S rDNA tree was also calculated for comparison.

207

208 *Computational performance*

209 The computational performance of *bcgTree* on sets with different numbers of
210 complete genomes was assessed on a standard dual-core desktop computer
211 (Intel(R) Core(TM)2 Duo CPU E8500, 4GB RAM, *Ubuntu* 14.04.3 LTS 64bit). Since
212 *bcgTree* is designed to work on complete genomes and has a fixed set of 107
213 essential genes, the only variable is the number of genomes. Genome size
214 variation is not expected to change the overall runtime substantially and was not
215 evaluated.

216 The pipeline was executed on a variable number of genomes: for five to fifteen
217 genomes, each step-size of one was repeated with five replicates, for five to fifty
218 genomes only one replicate was done with a step-size of five. For all steps,

219 random proteomes were selected from all data downloaded from the genome
220 database of *NCBI*. The total runtime of *bcgTree* was further separated into time
221 before and after start of *RAxML*, to estimate the proportion of preparation and
222 tree calculation of the total runtime. Linearity of the runtime increase with
223 number of genomes was tested using a linear model for complete and pre-*RAxML*
224 runtime.

225

226 Results and Discussion

227 Case study: *Lactobacillus* phylogeny

228 The case-study tree automatically generated by *bcgTree* largely supports the
229 monophyly of most genera within the Lactobacillales (Fig. 2). However,
230 *Pediococcus* (9 genomes) and the family Leuconostocaceae (51 genomes that
231 form a monophylum and include the genera *Weissella*, *Oenococcus*, *Fructobacillus*,
232 *Leuconostoc*) get inserted into the *Lactobacillus* genus, thus violating the
233 monophyly of the latter. This is a known phenomenon that can also be observed
234 in the All-Species Living Tree (Yarza et al., 2008). Within the genus *Lactobacillus*,
235 the tree is well resolved and consistent with previously published results on the
236 genus (Kant et al., 2011). Most species are well resolved into monophyletic
237 clusters with high support values, thus providing better assignments than 16S
238 only based analyses (Yarza et al., 2008), yet the All-Species Living Tree contains
239 only a single representative of most *Lactobacillus* species.

240 The *bcgTree* phylogeny also supports the three major groups of *Lactobacillus*
241 species as listed in vol. 3 of Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology (Vos et
242 al., 2011) and Kant et al. (2011) (*L. delbrueckii* group or NCFM, *L. reuteri* group or
243 WCFS1, *L. salivarius* group or WCFS2, and *L. rhamnosus/casei* group or GG) as
244 monophyla with some new species added. The WCFS group reported by Kant et
245 al. (2011) is split in the *bcgTree* tree into two groups separated by the
246 Leuconostocaceae, which were not considered in that study. Furthermore, there
247 are *Lactobacillus* strains that do not belong to any of these groups. Within the *L.*
248 *rhamnosus/casei* group, *L. casei* (22 genomes) and *L. paracasei* (37 genomes), the
249 leaves of the tree were highly intermixed, suggesting that it might not be
250 appropriate to assign these to different species.

251

252 *Comparison to 16S topology*

253 For the low-taxonomy evaluation set of *Lactobacillus*, bootstrap support values
254 were consistently higher with *bcgTree* than 16S data only (Supplementary File 2,
255 $t = 2.25$, $df = 27$, $p < 0.05^*$ and Fig. 3). The presence/absence results of the
256 *bcgTree* procedure with *Lactobacillus* show two genomes that lack a high
257 proportion of the included genes (Supplementary File 1). These were
258 *Lactobacillus fermentum* CECT 5716 and *Lactobacillus salviarius* CECT 5713. Both
259 genomes are of typical sizes suggesting that they have been well assembled. They
260 showed however a reduction by approximately one half of predicted open
261 reading frames indicating incomplete annotation. Thus the proteome files were
262 smaller than those of closely related taxa. Still the tree reconstruction with
263 *bcgTree* assigned them adequately at their expected positions in the trees, and
264 was robust with high bootstrap values. This indicates that the tool is resilient to
265 missing gene predictions in the proteome files. Also, some genes are represented
266 by two HMMs and in almost all cases a hit was found for only one HMM per gene.

267 For the second evaluation set on a high taxonomy level, the *bcgTree* tree
268 outperformed the 16S rDNA tree in terms of robustness with bootstrap support
269 values (Supplementary File 3, $t = 6.31$, $df = 93$, $p < 0.001^{***}$ and Fig. 3). The
270 general topology of the *bcgTree* tree was in concordance with the currently
271 prevailing opinion of bacterial phylogeny. The *bcgTree* tree results provided
272 support for monophyly of the two gram-positive groups Firmicutes and
273 Actinobacteria. These groups were not resolved using 16S sequences alone. Also
274 the Spirochaetes, PVC and FCB cluster together only with *bcgTree*, which is the
275 current consensus opinion of the relatedness of these clades according to
276 Bergey's Taxonomic Outlines (Ludwig et al., 2010). The remaining clades were
277 resolved consistently with both methods, although with slightly different
278 arrangements between groups. Please consider however that this study does not
279 intend to resolve the molecular phylogeny of bacterial high-level groups and that
280 taxa were arbitrarily chosen to validate the utility of the *bcgTree* approach for
281 higher-level taxonomy.

282

283 *Multi-marker benefits*

284 For both evaluation sets, we subsampled the numbers of genes randomly and
285 compared the resulting trees with the tree calculated on the complete gene set to
286 infer influences of gene number on the accuracy of the method. In both
287 evaluation sets, the Quartet-Distance of trees calculated on subsets of the genes
288 strongly decreases with an increase in the number of genes included (see Fig. 4).
289 This shows that including more genes has great impact and benefits the accuracy
290 of obtaining a tree similar to the full gene set. In both sets it can be seen that
291 including five genes already leads to a great improvement in comparison to single
292 gene analyses and this benefit appears to continually increase with more genes.
293 The Quartet-Distance of the 16S rDNA *Lactobacillus* tree is higher than most of
294 the *bcgTree*-derived trees calculated with even small subsets of the essential
295 genes. In contrast for the high level taxonomy example the 16S rDNA tree has a
296 lower Quartet-Distance than most of the small subset trees but a higher Quartet-
297 Distance than the *bcgTree* trees constructed using the full 107 genes and large
298 subsets of the genes. This observation highlights the suitability of 16S rDNA as a
299 marker for high level taxonomy while demonstrating that the single-marker 16S
300 rDNA analyses can be improved upon through multi-marker approaches, such as
301 *bcgTree*.

302 For our case-study the mean number and standard deviation of genes identified
303 and used per genome was 104.0 +/- 6.4. For the low-level as well as the high-
304 level evaluation sets this was 104.9 +/- 9.0 and 99.4 +/- 21.5, respectively. The
305 low values in the low-level evaluation set is explained by the inclusion of a
306 parasitic organism into the test set, which has a reduced genome

307

308 *Computational performance*

309 The computational time for the preliminary preparation steps including HMM
310 searches and alignments, increased linearly with each additional genome ($t =$
311 155.597, $df = 63$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001^{***}$, $R^2 = 0.98$) and the best fit line for this
312 relationship exhibited a slope of 16.9 seconds/genome. The total runtime was
313 also found to be significantly correlated with a linear model ($t = 45.9$, $df = 63$, $p <$
314 0.001^{***} , $R^2 = 0.97$) and this relationship exhibited a slope of 709.9

315seconds/genome, although non-linear increases were observable for low-
316genome numbers (Fig. 5). This may be due to general *RAxML* initialization steps
317that are independent of data amount and are thus proportionally
318overrepresented with the low-genome-number analyses. In general, it can be
319assumed that the tree-building step, not the *bcgTree* specific tasks, consumes the
320largest fraction of the runtime.

321In the current setup a phylogenetic tree from core genomes of fifty organisms can
322be calculated on a standard desktop computer in less than 24 hours. For larger
323analyses, the runtime can be decreased by using alternative tree calculation
324software or the high-performance computing variant *ExaML* that parallelizes
325tasks on different computer nodes.

326Comparison with existing tools

327The challenge of comparing whole genomes of bacteria has been undertaken
328through different approaches. One approach is to limit the scope to very closely
329related species to have large sets of orthologous genes. This approach is used by
330ATGC (Novichkov et al., 2009), which provides pre-calculated alignments for
331whole genomes from *NCBI RefSeq* (Pruitt et al., 2007). This way, a large amount of
332information is available for each cluster (e.g. 1500 orthologous genes for
333*Lactobacillus*), providing a solid basis for micro-evolutionary analyses. Yet, only a
334very limited number of taxa can be included in ATGC analyses, for example only
335eleven *Lactobacillus* genomes. Also, ATGC is not designed to do analyses across
336clusters. The eleven *Lactobacillus* genomes are split over four clusters, so a
337comparison across the whole genus or with closely related genera is not
338practical. Further, including user-provided datasets in ATGC is not possible. In
339summary, ATGC can help answering micro-evolutionary questions, but is limited
340for broader phylogenetic research questions.

341Another approach is to use alignment-free methods using composition vectors,
342as implemented in *CVTree* (Zuo and Hao, 2015). By dropping the alignment step
343many potential bioinformatic challenges (like length-hypervariable genes) can be
344avoided and the distances between genomes can be rapidly calculated. However,
345whilst more sequences are included (typically all proteins of a genome), the
346position information of each amino acid is dropped and thus a great amount of

347information ignored. As a consequence, the overall information content is quite
348different to the approach described in this article and might yield different
349results. We suggest using both the alignment-free and our alignment-based
350approach together for phylogenetic studies on whole genomes. Both methods are
351valid and may provide complementary and supportive viewpoints on bacterial
352phylogenies.

353

354**Conclusions**

355As demonstrated by the case study and evaluation, bacterial phylogenies can be
356accurately and robustly reconstructed using our automated pipeline
357implemented in *bcgTree*. By using 107 single-copy essential genes, the resolution
358is not limited to either lower or higher taxonomic ranks. The good results on both
359a fine scale (*Lactobacillus*) and a coarse scale (major bacterial groups)
360demonstrate its potential and versatility. It circumvents the restrictions that
361apply to single-marker phylogenies and also eases and standardizes the
362processes to perform whole-genome phylogenies with bacteria. The tool is freely
363available for download and use at the *github* repository
364<https://github.com/iimog/bcgTree> and our institutional homepage
365<http://www.dna-analytics.biozentrum.uni-wuerzburg.de>.

366

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373

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465 **Figures**
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467 Figure 1: Schematic workflow of the *bcgTree* pipeline.

468Figure 2: Case study tree calculated with *bcgTree* containing 515 Lactobacillales
469genomes. Numbers at nodes designate bootstrap support values resulting from
470100 bootstrap replicates. Outgroup is *Aerococcus*. Monophyletic genera and
471species have been collapsed as <g> and <s>, respectively (represented as a
472triangle considering intra-group variation as distance, with number of included
473genomes in curly brackets).

474Figure 3: Bootstrap support values for *bcgTree* and 16S rDNA only for direct
475comparison. Both evaluation sets, i.e. high-level and low-level taxonomy are
476displayed.

477Fig 4: Accuracy errors according to the Quartet-Distance between trees of
478variable numbers of genes (1-108) and the trees based on the complete set. For
479each number of genes 10 replicates were performed and for visualization
480purposes, the number of genes was rounded to increments of five. In addition the
481Quartet-Distance of the 16S rDNA tree is shown.

482Figure 5: Runtime of *bcgTree* for varying numbers of genomes in the tree
483calculation process with or without RAxML.

484

Bootstrap Support

Supplementary File 1: presence/absence matrix of essential core genes found for the *Lactobacillus* dataset. Rows are genes and columns are genomes.

Supplementary File 2: Evaluation set 1 tree including all currently deposited *Lactobacillus* genomes in NCBI (Nov 2015). Left side: bcgTree, right side: 16S rRNA only. Numbers at nodes designate bootstrap support values. Dashed lines represent inconsistency, in terms of topology changes, between the two approaches in terms of tree topology. Colored lines indicate clades consistently resolved by both methods by colors and connect same taxa between the two trees. Outgroup is *Paenibacillus*.

Supplementary File 3: Evaluation set 2 tree including two genera from each of the major bacterial groups. Left side: bcgTree, right side: 16S rRNA only. Numbers at nodes designate bootstrap support values. Dashed lines represent inconsistency, in terms of topology changes, between the two approaches in terms of tree topology. Colored lines indicate clades consistently resolved by both methods by colors and connect same taxa between the two trees. g+: gram positive bacteria, Firm: Firmicutes, Act: Actinobacteria, Spiro: Spirochaetes, PVC: PVC-Group, FCB: FCB-Group, Prot: Proteobacteria, Ther: Thermotogae. Outgroup is Archaea.